

An efficient protocol for synthesis of 4-methoxy cinnamate in ionic liquid

Yu Fang Wang^a, Qi Chao Yang^{a,b}, Bao Ji Zhang^a, Dong Lin^a and Ming Jie Zhang^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, School of Science, Tianjin University, Tianjin 300072, China

E-mail : mjzhangtju@163.com Fax : 86-022-27403475

^bChemistry and Pharmaceutical Engineering College, Nanyang Normal University, Nanyang 473061, China

Manuscript received online 18 April 2012, revised 08 June 2012, accepted 13 June 2012

Abstract : Synthesis of 2-ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate was carried out efficiently using palladium-catalyzed Heck reaction of 4-bromoanisole and 2-ethylhexylacrylate in tetrabutyl ammonium bromide-based ionic liquid. The ionic liquid was used as a cost-effective reaction medium and the catalyst in it is stable and can be recycled for at least four times without significant loss in activity.

Keywords : 2-Ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate, Heck reaction, ionic liquid, recycled.

Introduction

2-Ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate (OMC) is a UV-B absorbing compound which is important in the flavors, perfumes, cosmetics, graphics and pharmaceutical industries^{1,2}. Thus, many patents³⁻⁶ and papers^{7,8} are reported for the synthesis of it. But these methods show various disadvantages, such as using of expensive materials, high boiling solvents and low yields.

Palladium-catalyzed coupling of olefins with aryl and vinyl halides, known as the Heck reaction is one of the most important C-C bond forming reactions⁹. Despite of its applications and usefulness, there are some drawbacks about this reaction. It is difficult to carry out the reaction when using the deactivated aryl bromides or aryl chlorides for coupling with the less reactive long-chain acrylates¹⁰⁻¹². In order to overcome these disadvantages, Heck reaction generally proceeds under high temperature and bulky phosphorus ligands are needed to assist the initial oxidative-addition of C-X bond. However, under high temperature phosphorus and their palladium complexes are prone to decomposition. Hence it is necessary to develop a suitable alternative for these expensive ligands and develop a simple and cost-effective alternative for Heck reaction of deactivated aryl halide with long-chain acrylates. Ionic liquid is one of the best choices. Recently, ionic liquids are extensively used as the solvent for the Heck reaction and become popular, due to their

good solvating ability, negligible vapor pressure and easy catalyst recycling¹³⁻¹⁵.

Herein, we report that using tetrabutyl ammonium bromide as ionic liquid for palladium-catalyzed Heck reaction to synthesize 2-ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate (Scheme 1) and the ionic liquid and catalyst can be reused for at least four times.

Results and discussion

For the standardization of reaction conditions, several bases were tested such as NaOAc, K₃PO₄ and Bu₃N. Results in Table 1 showed that Bu₃N had positive influence without exhibiting large differences in product yield compared to other bases (Table 1, entry 3). The reaction in molten [nBu₄N]Br without Bu₃N was considered as reference. At such reaction conditions product was obtained with the yield of 66% after 4 h (Table 1, entry 4). Bu₃N as an organic base can resolve the reactant more efficiently, and this observation allowed to conclude that the effect of eventually formed nBu₃N as the product of thermal decomposition of [nBu₄N]Br → nBu₃N + nBuBr can be neglected¹⁶. Decreasing the catalyst to 0.5 mol% still gave a respectable 85% yield of the product (Table 1, entry 9). When the reaction was performed for an extended period of time (16 h), 0.2 mol% of Pd/C was found to be sufficient to give a high conversion with 88% yield of the product (Table 1, entry 10).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate.

Table 1. Synthesis of OMC with *p*-bromoanisole and 2-ethylhexylacrylate^a

Entry	Solvent	Base	mol% Pd/C	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^b
1	TBAB	NaOAc	1.0	2	70
2	TBAB	NaOAc	1.0	4	89
3	TBAB	ⁿ Bu ₃ N	1.0	4	98
4	TBAB	-	1.0	4	66
5	TBAB	K ₃ PO ₄	1.0	2	68
6	TBAB	K ₃ PO ₄	1.0	4	93
7	CTAB	ⁿ Bu ₃ N	1.0	4	67
8	(C ₆ Py)Cl	ⁿ Bu ₃ N	1.0	4	79
9	TBAB	ⁿ Bu ₃ N	0.5	4	85
10	TBAB	ⁿ Bu ₃ N	0.2	16	88

^a*p*-Bromoanisole 1.0 mmol, 2-ethylhexylacrylate 1.2 mmol, base 1.2 mmol, solvent 1.5 mmol, *T* = 120 °C. ^bGC-MS yield based on *p*-bromoanisole.

The efficiency of various molten salts as solvents (Table 1, entry 7 and 8) and other polar organic solvents (Table 2) for this reaction was examined, in terms of productivity and stability of the catalyst, TBAB performed best compared to other solvents and was cost-effective. Several other solvents including DMF, NMP, DMA and 1,4-dioxane were also tested under similar conditions but all gave inferior results compared to TBAB (Table 2). Comparison of yields obtained with Pd/C in ionic liquid with those obtained in NMP or DMF showed that OMC can be obtained.

The reaction of aryl iodine and aryl chlorine with 2-ethylhexylacrylate was also carried out under the best conditions found for the reaction of aryl bromide (Scheme 2, Table 3). Aryl iodine could get a yield of 99%, with-

Table 2 Effect of solvents on the yield of coupling of *p*-bromoanisole with 2-ethylhexylacrylate in molten TBAB^a

Entry	Solvent	Yield (%) ^b
1	DMA	38
2	DMF	73
3	NMP	48
4	1,4-Dioxane ^c	54
5	TBAB ^d	98

^a*p*-Bromoanisole 1.0 mmol, 2-ethylhexylacrylate 1.2 mmol, Pd/C 1.0 mol%, base 1.2 mmol, solvent 3 mL, *T* = 120 °C, 4 h. ^bGC-MS yield based on *p*-bromoanisole. ^cThis reaction was performed at 100 °C. ^dTBAB 1.5 mmol.

out notable difference from aryl bromide (Table 3, entry 3). But aryl bromide as reactant is more economical than aryl iodine. When the reaction was carried out on aryl chlorine substrates using the optimal conditions developed for the aryl bromide, low yields of the coupled product were obtained in 65% (Table 3, entry 4) and 67% (catalyzed by PdCl₂ at 140 °C) (Table 3, entry 5), respectively.

In addition, the ionic liquid layer containing the Pd catalyst was shown to be active and reusable. The catalyst was recovered at the end of reaction and recycled four runs without loss of activity and selectivity. In our opinion the reason of the observed decrease of catalytic activity is associated with accumulation of NaBr, the side product which was not extracted with ethyl acetate from reaction mixture during recycling procedure.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents used were analytical grade material obtained from market and were used without

Scheme 2

Table 3 Coupling of different aryl halide with 2-ethylhexylacrylate in TBAB^a

Entry	Aryl halide	T (°C)	Yield (%) ^b
1		120	98
2		140 ^c	88
3		120	99
4		120	65
5		140 ^d	67

^aAryl halide 1.0 mmol, 2-ethylhexylacrylate 1.2 mmol, Pd/C 1.0 mol%, ⁿBu₃N 1.2 mmol, solvent 1.5 mmol, T = 120 °C, 4 h. ^bGC-MS yield based on *p*-bromoanisole. ^cCatalyzed by PdCl₂. ^dCatalyzed by PdCl₂, T = 140 °C.

further purification. The synthesized compound was previously reported, and identified by spectroscopic data, and by comparison with available standards. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a JEOL 400 MHz spectrometer with tetramethyl silane (TMS) as internal standard.

Preparation of 2-ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate :

p-Bromoanisole (1 mmol), 2-ethylhexylacrylate (1.2 mmol), ⁿBu₃N (1.2 mmol), and Pd/C catalyst (0.01 mmol) (1.0 mol% relative to substrate) were stirred in [ⁿBu₄N]Br

(1.5 mmol) at 120 °C under nitrogen atmosphere for 4 h (for aryl chloride substrates, the reaction temperature was maintained at 140 °C). The progress of the coupling reaction was monitored by TLC. After the completion of reaction, the organic products form an upper phase layer that was extracted with ethyl acetate and analyzed by GC-MS. The precipitate was separated by simple filtration and washed sufficiently with ethyl acetate for three times, then dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C for 4 h. The catalysts were recovered and reused in the next run without further activation treatment. Vacuum distillation afforded pure OMC (78% yield); b.p. 180 ~ 185 °C at 1.00 mm Hg.

Spectroscopic data :

2-Ethylhexyl-4-methoxy cinnamate : ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 7.63 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 7.19 (4H, AA'BB' quartet, aromatic), 6.31 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 4.11 (2H, d), 3.83 (3H, s), 1.67–1.31 (15H, m).

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we found it was a new and available synthetic route to OMC that *p*-bromoanisole coupled with 2-ethylhexylacrylate with Pd/C as catalyst in TBAB. TBAB as an excellent media and Pd/C as catalyst for the preparation of OMC have various advantages. The TBAB is more economical and increases the stabilization and activation of the catalyst (Pd/C), allowing for ionic liquid and catalyst recycling. Future studies in our laboratory will focus on exploring the full scope of this reaction.

References

1. G. Lee, A. Widjaja and Y. Ju, *Biotechnology Letters*, 2006, **28**, 581.
2. M. Aslam, W. F. Stansbury, R. J. Reiter and D. R. Larkin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1997, **62**, 1550.
3. A. Anatoly and C. Ratan, "Process for Preparation of Cinnamate Sunscreen Agents", US Patent 5527947, 1996.
4. C. Douglas, "Process for Producing 2-ethylhexyl-*p*-methoxycinnamate", US Patent 4970332, 1990.
5. G. Peter, "Process for the Manufacture of Cinnamic Acid Derivatives", US Patent 5457226, 1995.
6. J. C. Alan, A. V. Joseph, W. Laszlo and B. W. Theresa, "Process for the Palladium Catalyzed Coupling of a Diazonium Salt with an Olefinic Bond", US Patent 5274171, 1993.
7. B. List, A. Doehring, M. H. Fonseca, A. Job and R. R. Torres, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **61**, 476.
8. H. Brunner, N. L. Cousturie and J. Genet, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 4815.
9. Q. Yao, E. Kinney and Z. Yang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 7528.
10. C. Yang, H. M. Lee and S. Nolan, *Org. Lett.*, 2001, **3**, 1511.
11. A. Littke and G. Fu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 6989.
12. S. Li, Y. Lin, H. Xie, S. Zhang and J. Xu, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 391.
13. F. Bellina and C. Chiappe, *Molecules*, 2010, **15**, 2211.
14. S. Liu and J. Xiao, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **270**, 1.
15. A. Carmichael, M. Earle, J. Holbrey, P. McCormac and K. Seddon, *Organic Lett.*, 1999, **1**, 997.
16. I. Pryjomska-Ray and A. Trzeciak, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **257**, 3.